

Multiobjective energy management of multi-source offshore parks assisted with hybrid battery and hydrogen/fuel-cell energy storage systems

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HIGHLIGHTS

- A multiobjective energy management framework is proposed for hybrid offshore parks.
- Hybrid storage system including batteries, hydrogen, and fuel-cell is applied.
- Different scenarios are modeled regarding the limitations in the electrical system.
- Joint and split offshore/onshore implementation of storage systems are considered.
- Renewable energy delivery is maximized while decreasing power fluctuations.

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ABSTRACT

With the recent advancements in the development of hybrid offshore parks and the expected large-scale implementation of them in the near future, it becomes paramount to investigate proper energy management strategies to improve the integrability of these parks into the power systems. This paper addresses a multi-objective energy management approach using a hybrid energy storage system comprising batteries and hydrogen/fuel-cell systems applied to multi-source wind-wave and wind-solar offshore parks to maximize the delivered energy while minimizing the variations of the power output. To find the solution of the optimization problem defined for energy management, a strategy is proposed based on the examination of a set of weighting factors to form the Pareto front while the problem associated with each of them is assessed in a mixed-integer linear programming framework. Subsequently, fuzzy decision making is applied to select the final solution among the ones existing in the Pareto front. The studies are implemented in different locations considering scenarios for electrical system limitation and the place of the storage units. According to the results, applying the proposed multiobjective framework successfully addresses the enhancement of energy delivery and the decrease in power output fluctuations in the hybrid offshore parks across all scenarios of electrical system limitation and combinational storage locations. Based on the results, in addition to the increase in delivered energy, a decrease in power variations by around 40 % up to over 80 % is observed in the studied cases.

1. Introduction

The ever more urgent need for the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions, due to the risk of exacerbating climate change, has been pushing the energy sector towards decarbonization, that is the detachment from the dependency of energy production on fossil fuels towards less emissive technologies. The current targets set by the European Union (EU) are a reduction in greenhouse gas emissions of 55 % by 2030

and the achievement of climate neutrality by 2050 [1]. In this context, an impressive increase in installed capacity of Renewable Energy Sources (RES) has been observed since the beginning of the millennium, and exceeded the 40 % of gross final energy consumption in some European countries in 2022, being even more than 60 % in cases like Sweden [2].

In particular, offshore sites demonstrate significant potential for harvesting renewable energies [3]. Sea or ocean locations are generally characterized by a higher wind resource availability than on-land sites

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Nomenclature**Abbreviations**

BESS	Battery Energy Storage System
ESS	Energy Storage System
FC	Fuel Cell
FDM	Fuzzy Decision Making
FPV	Floating Photovoltaic
H ₂	Hydrogen
MILP	Mixed Integer Linear Programming
MO	Multi Objective
NS	No-Storage case
OF	Objective Function
RES	Renewable Energy Source
SoC	State of Charge
SoH	State of Hydrogen
WEC	Wave Energy Converter
WT	Wind Turbine

Parameters

A_{WT}	Area swept by WT blades
A_{FPV}	Area of each FPV panel
C_p	Power coefficient of WT
E_{TDE}^{min}	Level of guaranteed delivered energy
E_{TVP}^{max}	Level assigned for the maximum TVP
EEL	Energy consumed by electrolyzer
ELH	Overall energy consumed for production of liquid hydrogen
ELP	Energy consumed in the liquefaction units
EWT	Energy consumed in water treatment unit
E_B^r	Energy capacity of BESS
G^t	Solar irradiance in hour t
M_H^r	Capacity of hydrogen tank
n	Number of OFs
n_{FPV}	Number of FPV panels
n_{WT}	Number of WTs
P_B^r	Rated power of BESS
P_C^r	Capacity of the cable
P_{FC}^r	Rated power of FC
P_H^r	Rated power of hydrogen production system
P_N^{max}	Maximum deliverable power to the network
P_{WT}^r	Rated power of WTs in the park
$P_{WT.ref}^r$	Rated power of reference WT
$P_{FPV,P}^t$	Power generation potential of FPVs in hour t
P_{RP}^t	Power generation potential of the RESs in hour t
$P_{WEC,P}^t$	Power generation potential of WECs in hour t

$P_{WT,P}^t$	Power generation potential of WTs in hour t
$P_{WT.ref,P}^t$	Power generation potential of the reference WT in hour t
PR_{FPV}	Performance ratio of the FPV panels
TDE_{NS}	Total delivered energy in the NS case
TVP_{NS}	TVP calculated for NS case
w_i	Weight of F_i as the representative of i th OF
WS^{in}	Cut-in speed of WT
WS^{out}	Cut-out speed of WT
WS^r	Rated wind speed of WT
WS^t	Wind speed in hour t
Δt	Time step duration
$\eta_{BC,x}$	Charging efficiency of BESS
$\eta_{BD,x}$	Discharging efficiency of BESS
η_{FPV}	Efficiency of the FPV panel
μ_{ri}	Reference value for the i th OF
ρ	Air density

Variables

$DTVP$	Decrease of the TVP
$E_{B,x}^t$	Energy stored in BESS in hour t
$I_{BC,x}^t$	Binary variable for charging mode of BESS in hour t
$I_{BD,x}^t$	Binary variable for discharging mode of BESS in hour t
$m_{in,x}^t$	Input mass rate of hydrogen to the tank in hour t
$m_{out,x}^t$	Output mass rate of hydrogen from the tank in hour t
M_x^t	Mass of hydrogen stored in the tank in hour t
$P_{BC,x}^t$	Charging power of the BESS system in hour t
$P_{BD,x}^t$	Discharging power of the BESS system in hour t
P_C^t	Power delivered through the cable in hour t
$P_{FC,x}^t$	Power generated by the FC in hour t
P_{FPV}^t	Power generated by FPVs in hour t
$P_{H,x}^t$	Power consumed in the hydrogen production units in hour t
P_N^t	Power delivered from park to network in hour t
P_R^t	Power generated by RESs inside the park in hour t
P_{RC}^t	Curtailed power in hour t
$P_{S,off}^t$	Power of offshore storage systems in hour t
$P_{S,on}^t$	Power of onshore storage systems in hour t
P_{WEC}^t	Power generated by WECs in hour t
P_{WT}^t	Power generated by WTs in hour t
TDE	Total delivered energy of the park
TVP	Total variation of power
VP^t	Variation of power of the park in hour t compared to previous hour

[4]. Furthermore, as described in [5], the space in the sea area for constructing RES parks can be bigger than the ones available onshore, which are restricted by populated and industrial areas. As technology advances, marine sources like wave and tidal energy are also being investigated as reliable sources for clean energy generation [6]. Several prototypes for capturing marine energy are currently implemented successfully proving their capabilities in contributing towards decarbonization of the energy sector. Due to the importance of research in this area, recent literature also includes studies on digitalization and the application of digital twins for modelling and assessing marine energy sources [7].

Regarding the stated benefits, the EU is also promoting the energy generation by offshore RESs; in 2020 a target for 2030 was set with the goal of 60 GW installed offshore wind (half of which was reached in 2022 [8]), and 1 GW of wave/tidal energy RESs [9]. Furthermore, in

recent years, an interest has been drawn in the co-location of RESs due to the technical and economic benefits that can be provided by the implementation of them in the same parks [10]. The more effective utilization of the common infrastructures and cost sharing are some of the potential advantages of installing different RES technologies in the same offshore park. Accordingly, the benefits deriving from the addition of offshore Floating Photovoltaic (FPV) panels [11] and Wave Energy Converters (WECs) [12] to existing offshore wind farms are evaluated concerning the capacity factor of the submarine cable in the literature. A stochastic sizing framework for hybridization of existing offshore wind farms is also developed in [13] maximizing the economic profits considering the uncertainty of renewable energy generation. The potential temporal complementarity in the energy generation by the different natural resources, which decreases the overall variability of the power output of the RES parks, is the other initiative for the

development of the idea of the hybrid RES parks [14]. In [15], combinational assessments are done on the decrease in the power variations and low-power hours as well as improvements in space utilization and cable capacity factor by the implementation of the hybrid sources in offshore parks.

Despite the power-smoothing potential of the hybrid RES parks, the wind, wave, and solar resources are still characterized by uncertainty and variability, reflecting on the parks' power output. In order to tackle this problem to provide a stable operation of electrical networks considering massive RES integration, Energy Storage Systems (ESS) are crucial parts of the future energy systems. In context of renewable energy parks, different ESS technologies are assessed in the literature depending on the specific applications. In [16], a framework is proposed for sizing the Battery Energy Storage Systems (BESSs) in offshore wind parks focusing on the economic assessment of the project. The suitability of a wide set of ESS technologies for offshore parks is addressed in [17] by identifying and rating the features relevant to this application. The outcome of this study highlights BESS and Hydrogen (H₂) as the two most favorable choices, and points out the complementarity between their features, and their different time of action; hence, emphasizing on BESS as the effective storage strategy in intra-day time-scale and H₂ in the longer periods, it is concluded that the combinational implementation of these ESS technologies can be beneficial to tackle the uncertainties of RES parks. With a similar strategy, in [18], the optimization of hybrid ESS is implemented where BESSs are combined with the H₂ production/storage systems to sell hydrogen directly to its specific market.

As a seasonal storage system supporting the electrical grid, the combinational implementation of Fuel Cells (FCs) besides the H₂ system is also addressed in the literature. FC for reconvert the H₂ produced by a wind farm to electricity is considered in [19]; similarly, in [20], H₂ systems with FC are applied to assist BESSs to meet the demand all over the year. By applying FC to reconvert the stored hydrogen to electricity, an optimal sizing of wind farm with hybrid BESS, H₂, and FC system is also performed in [21].

Besides the importance of technology selection and the determination of the optimal size, smart energy management is also necessary to effectively utilize ESSs in the RES parks [22]. The energy management strategy can be characterized by ensuring the supply of a required demand profile [23], maximizing economic profits [24], maximizing the delivered energy by decreasing the curtailments [26], decreasing power output fluctuations [25], or addressing any other preferred technical criteria or objective [27]. A real-time control strategy of ESS is presented in [28] for a RES-fed grid to minimize curtailments and mitigate forecasting errors. A comparison between a heuristic rule-based approach and a Mixed Integer Linear Programming (MILP) optimization strategy considering a priori knowledge of generation and demand data is presented in [29] to address the energy management of a BESS for a wind power plant connected to an islanded network. While these works focusing on energy management do not consider the possibility of the implementation of a hybrid battery-hydrogen ESS to tackle both short and long term output power variations, such a combination of ESSs is applied in [30] in RES-based microgrids; accordingly, an energy management strategy is developed based on a fuzzy logic controller, that succeeded in supplying the load demand while achieving a higher level of profitability and efficiency. Focusing on multi-ESS offshore parks, in [31], energy management is implemented for the park with Wind Turbines (WTs) and marine-current energy sources to match the load demand through a BESS-ultracapacitor hybrid ESS.

Regarding the implementation of ESSs in hybrid power plants [31], there are also other studies in the literature focusing on these storage-aided parks including multiple RESs. The benefits of a hybrid ESS in terms of the improvement of the power output stability in a hybrid wind and Photovoltaic (PV) park are evaluated in [32]. An optimization on the combination of WTs and PVs to minimize the mismatch between power supply and demand, together with the optimal sizing of a BESS, is

addressed in [33]. A techno-economic assessment of a hybrid wind-wave park assisted with different technologies of ESS is also given in [34] assessing their suitability to be installed offshore. A sizing/energy-management framework for BESS in hybrid wind-solar parks is also proposed in [35] where revenues from selling renewable energy are applied to the objective function. While these studies focus on a single objective for optimization, addressing a set of them is more common in real-world applications; however, as they can be in contrast, trade-off on the satisfaction level of each of them is also necessary for a Multi-Objective (MO) strategy.

In this paper, an MO energy management framework is proposed for multisource offshore parks assisted with hybrid BESS and H₂-FC storage systems. The energy management in this paper is studied from the point of view of the grid operator aiming at increasing renewable energy generation and reducing output power fluctuations. The hybrid ESS is considered to be placed whether in a concentrated configuration, altogether onshore or offshore, or to be split between in the two locations while the limitation in the capacities of the offshore cable and the onshore connection points are also considered. A solution strategy is developed based on the transformation of the MO problem to a set of single-objective MILP ones by applying weighting factors while examining them to estimate the Pareto front. Finally, Fuzzy Decision Making (FDM) is used to select the solution among the ones in the Pareto front. The proposed energy management strategy is applied to different offshore parks in different marine areas in the presence of the hybrid RESs; scenarios are considered on the location of the storage system units, electrical system capacity limitation, and the priorities of the decision maker while a comparison of the results is also provided.

The comparison of the current work with the existing literature is given in Table 1, which mostly focuses on offshore studies; however, onshore RES parks are not excluded. Furthermore, the sizing optimization studies integrating energy management are also included in the comparisons. However, since the sizing optimization part is out of the scope of the current work, the specifications of these studies are given concentrating on the energy management part of their model.

Based on the descriptions, the contributions of the study are summarized as follows:

- A new MO framework is proposed for energy management of hybrid offshore parks comprising WECs or FPVs besides the WTs to maximize the RES energy delivery to the network while minimizing the overall power output variations.
- An MILP model, while applying weighting factors to the MO problem, is developed for the energy management of the storage-assisted hybrid offshore parks considering the capacity limitation in the onshore connection point as well as the rated power of the offshore cable.
- The model is developed for energy management while considering the presence of the hybrid storage system including BESS and H₂-FC units, whether split or concentrated, placed in the offshore and/or onshore sectors.
- The effect of decision maker priorities on the energy delivered to the network and the power variations is investigated in the different scenarios of electrical system limitations and storage combinations in hybrid WT-WEC and WT-FPV offshore parks.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. The configuration of the hybrid energy storage system applied for the multi-source offshore RES park is described in Section 2. The mathematical model of the system and the optimization problem are presented in Section 3, followed by the description of the solution strategy in Section 4. The simulation studies are characterized, and the results of the optimizations are given and discussed in Section 5. Finally, conclusions are drawn in section 6.

Table 1
Comparison of the current work with the studies in the literature.

Ref.	Park configuration and RES sources		Electrical system limitations		Energy storage location			Objectives of energy management				Optimization				
	Hybrid	WT WEC PV	Offshore cable capacity	Onshore connection point	BESS	H2	FC	Offshore	Onshore	Both offshore and onshore	Energy max.	Revenue max.	Power variation min.	Load following	Multi-objective	Decision making
[11]	✓	×	✓	×	×	×	×	×	×	×	×	✓	×	×	×	×
[18]	×	×	×	✓	✓	×	×	×	✓	×	×	✓	×	×	×	×
[16]	×	×	✓	×	✓	×	×	×	×	×	×	✓	(constrained)	×	×	×
[23]	✓	×	×	×	✓	✓	×	×	×	×	×	×	×	✓	×	×
[19]	×	×	×	×	✓	✓	×	×	×	×	×	×	×	×	×	×
[31]	✓	×	×	×	✓	×	×	×	×	×	×	×	×	×	×	×
[34]	✓	×	×	×	✓	×	×	×	×	×	×	×	×	✓	×	×
[35]	✓	×	✓	×	✓	×	×	×	✓	×	×	×	×	×	×	×
This work	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	×	×	✓	FDM

* Not specified clearly.
** Surplus of power, with respect to the demand, is curtailed.

2. Hybrid storage system for multi-source offshore parks

The schematic of the multi-source RES park assisted with storage systems is given in Fig. 1. In this figure, P_R^t is the power of the RES sources inside the park (MW), $P_{S,off}^t$ is the power transaction of the offshore storage systems (MW), P_C^t is the power delivered through the cable to the inland network from the offshore site (MW), $P_{S,on}^t$ is the power of the onshore storage (MW), and P_N^t is the overall power delivered from the park to the electrical network (MW).

Regarding the RES sources, in general, the hybrid offshore park can be comprised of WTs, WECs, and FPVs as shown in Fig. 2 where P_{WT}^t , P_{WEC}^t , and P_{FPV}^t represent the power generation by WTs, WECs, and FPVs (MW). However, it should be emphasized that in this study, the combinational RES scenarios are limited to WT-WC and WT-FPV; accordingly, the WTs are always considered to be existing in the park. On the other hand, the presence of WECs and FPVs at the same time in the park is not considered to be an option in the studied scenarios.

Regardless of the place, the generic representation of the potential elements of the storage system is given in Fig. 3. The generic representation of the storage-aided hybrid park with the potential/candidate storage system units in the offshore/onshore sectors is given in Fig. 4. As represented, the H2-FC storage systems in this paper comprise three main units named H2 production, H2 storage, and the FC system. While $x \in \{on, off\}$ represents the location (i.e. onshore or offshore), $P_{BC,x}^t$ and $P_{BD,x}^t$ are the charging and discharging power of the BESS system (MW), $P_{H,x}^t$ is the power consumed in the hydrogen generation units (MW), $\dot{m}_{in,x}^t$ and $\dot{m}_{out,x}^t$ are the input and output mass rate of hydrogen into/from the tank (kg/h), and $P_{FC,x}^t$ is the power generated by the FC (MW), all in hour t of study. It should be noted that the H2 production system itself includes different subsystems in this study where further description of them can be found in [18].

As described before, and demonstrated in Fig. 4, the storage system can be placed offshore, onshore, or in both locations. Considering the hybrid storage system, each of them in the offshore or onshore sector can comprise a BESS and/or a H2-FC unit. However, the hybrid storage scenarios in this paper are limited to the cases as follows:

- Offshore BESS and offshore H2-FC
- Offshore BESS and onshore H2-FC
- Onshore BESS and onshore H2-FC

The generalized mathematical model of this system regarding the presence of the multiple RESs and the hybrid offshore/onshore storage systems as well as the methodology implemented to model the energy management framework are given in Section 3.

3. Mathematical model

The mathematical model for energy management in a multi-source offshore park using the hybrid storage system is given in this section. Accordingly, the overall system model is provided in Section 3.1 while the other details on the mathematical representation of the optimization study including the objective functions and the constraints are given in Section 3.2; finally, the model of the RES sources for the calculation of the potential of energy generation in the park is provided in Section 3.3.

Fig. 1. Generic representation of a multi-source offshore park assisted with potential/candidate onshore and offshore storage systems.

Fig. 2. Generic representation of the multi-source RES-based offshore parks.

Fig. 3. Generic representation of combinational BESS and H2-FC storage systems.

It should be emphasized that the mathematical model in this section is given in a generalized framework to include both offshore and onshore storage systems each comprising the BESS and H2-FC units. However, this is then re-adjusted for each study regarding the storage system scenario specifying the location of the BESS and H2-FC whether concentrated or distributed between the offshore and onshore sites.

3.1. Overall system model

According to Fig. 1, the power delivered to the network is calculated using (1).

$$P_N^t = P_C^t + P_{S,on}^t \quad (1)$$

where P_C^t , as the power delivered through the cable, is calculated by (2).

$$P_C^t = P_R^t + P_{S,off}^t \quad (2)$$

in which P_R^t , as shown in Fig. 2, can be represented by (3).

$$P_R^t = P_{WT}^t + P_{WEC}^t + P_{FPV}^t \quad (3)$$

It should be noted in this study, the curtailment of RES generation is also considered in the model that is represented by (4).

$$P_{RC}^t = P_{RP}^t - P_R^t \quad (4)$$

where P_{RC}^t is the curtailment of power in hour t (MW) while P_{RP}^t is the potential of power generation by the RES units (MW) in the same hour represented by (5).

$$P_{RP}^t = P_{WT,P}^t + P_{WEC,P}^t + P_{FPV,P}^t \quad (5)$$

where $P_{WT,P}^t$, $P_{WEC,P}^t$, and $P_{FPV,P}^t$ are the potential of power generation by WT, WEC, and FPV systems (MW). Based on Fig. 3, considering $x \in \{on, off\}$, the power from the hybrid storage system can be represented by (6).

$$P_{S,x}^t = P_{BD,x}^t - P_{BC,x}^t + P_{FC,x}^t - P_{H,x}^t \quad (6)$$

Considering the efficiencies of charging and discharging power in the BESS system, the stored energy is calculated using (7) [36].

$$E_{B,x}^t = E_{B,x}^{t-1} - \frac{P_{BD,x}^t \times \Delta t}{\eta_B} + \eta_B \times P_{BC,x}^t \times \Delta t \quad (7)$$

where $\eta_{BC,x}$ and $\eta_{BD,x}$ represent the charging and discharging efficiencies while $E_{B,x}^t$ is the energy stored in BESS in hour t (MWh), and Δt is the time step duration of the study that is 1 h in this paper.

The input and output mass rate of hydrogen into/from the storage tank can be represented as a function of the power input of the H2 production units and the power output of FC as represented in (8) [37] and (9) [38].

$$\dot{m}_{in,x}^t = \frac{P_{H,x}^t}{ELH} \quad (8)$$

$$\dot{m}_{out,x}^t = \frac{P_{FC,x}^t}{\alpha_{FC} \times \eta_{FC}} \quad (9)$$

in which ELH is the energy needed in the production of a unit mass of liquid hydrogen (MWh/kg) [37], α_{FC} is the energy produced by 1 kg of H2 (MWh/kg), and η_{FC} is the efficiency of the FC unit. Neglecting the auxiliary losses of the model in [37], ELH is calculated using (10).

$$ELH = EEL + EWT + ELP \quad (10)$$

where EEL , EWT , ELP are the energies consumed in the electrolyzer, water treatment unit, and liquefaction units. The hydrogen stored in the tank considering the input and output mass rates can be calculated using (11).

$$M_x^t = M_x^{t-1} + \left(\dot{m}_{in,x}^{t-1} - \dot{m}_{out,x}^{t-1} \right) \times \Delta t \quad (11)$$

where M_x^t is the mass of hydrogen stored in the tank (kg).

Fig. 4. Representation of the studied system with the potential/candidate onshore or offshore storage units.

3.2. Objective functions and constraints

The energy management of the storage system in this paper is applied to maximize the overall RES energy delivery and minimize the power fluctuations. The mathematical representation of the optimization problem defined for the energy management of the multi-source offshore park assisted with the hybrid energy storage system, including the objective functions and the constraints, is given in the following subsections.

3.2.1. Objectives functions

Regarding the descriptions given on the objectives of energy management in this paper, the OFs of the study are represented by (12) and (13).

$$OF_1 = TDE \quad (12)$$

$$OF_2 = TVP \quad (13)$$

where TDE and TVP are the total delivered energy of the park and the total power variations, calculated by (14) and (15), over the whole year that is 8760 h.

$$TDE = \sum_{i=1}^{8760} P_N^t \quad (14)$$

$$TVP = \sum_{i=2}^{8760} VP^t \quad (15)$$

in which VP^t is the variation of the output power of the park in hour t compared to the previous hour that is calculated using (16).

$$VP^t = |P_N^t - P_N^{t-1}| \quad (16)$$

Based on the descriptions, the overall MO representation of the problem is given as (17) and (18).

$$\text{Maximize } OF_1 \quad (17)$$

$$\text{Minimize } OF_2 \quad (18)$$

In order to present all the equations in the MILP framework, (16) is replaced with a set of constraints given as (19) and (20).

$$VP^t \geq P_N^t - P_N^{t-1} \quad (19)$$

$$VP^t \geq P_N^{t-1} - P_N^t \quad (20)$$

In order to provide a measure for the variation of power compared to the case where no storage existed in the park, a supplementary index is defined as the Decrease in the Total Variation of Power (DTVP) while being calculated using (21).

$$DTVP = \frac{TVP_{NS} - TVP}{TVP_{NS}} \times 100\% \quad (21)$$

where TVP_{NS} is the TVP calculated for No-Storage (NS) case.

3.2.2. Constraints

The main constraints applied to the optimization study of this paper are presented in this section. As the first constraint, the capacity limitation for the power injection into the network is considered in the model that is represented by (22).

$$0 \leq P_N^t \leq P_N^{\max} \quad (22)$$

in which P_N^{\max} is the maximum power that can be delivered to the network. The power flow from the offshore connection point to the onshore one is also limited by the capacity of the cable as represented in (23).

$$0 \leq P_C^t \leq P_C^r \quad (23)$$

In this paper, in order to prevent the excessive storage system operation and the lower overall efficiency of the park especially when the focus of MO is on the minimization of power fluctuations, a constraint is applied on TDE using (24).

$$TDE \geq d_{TDE}^{\min} \times TDE_{NS} \quad (24)$$

where d_{TDE}^{\min} is the level of guaranteed total delivered energy comparing the NS case represented by TDE_{NS} . Similarly, in order to guarantee the decrease of the overall power fluctuations, it is constrained using (25).

$$TVP \leq d_{TVP}^{\max} \times TVP_{NS} \quad (25)$$

where d_{TVP}^{\max} is the level assigned for the maximum TVP comparing the NS case.

As the next set of constraints, the charging/discharging power of BESS in the whole hours of operation is limited to the nominal value; along with the constraint on charging/discharging mode, these constraints are represented in (26)–(28) [39].

$$0 \leq P_{BC,x}^t \leq I_{BC,x}^t \times P_B^r \quad (26)$$

$$0 \leq P_{BD,x}^t \leq I_{BD,x}^t \times P_B^r \quad (27)$$

$$I_{BC,x}^t + I_{BD,x}^t \leq 1 \quad (28)$$

where $I_{BC,x}^t$ and $I_{BD,x}^t$ are binary variables representing the activation of the charging and discharging modes of BESS, and P_B^r is the rated power of it. Furthermore, the energy stored in BESS and the mass of hydrogen in the tank in each hour are also constrained with respect to both the rated capacities and the minimum allowed levels as represented in (29) and (30) applying the State of Charge (SoC) and State of Hydrogen (SoH) defined in (31) and (32), respectively.

$$SoC_x^{\min} \leq SoC_x^t \leq 1 \quad (29)$$

$$SoH_x^{\min} \leq SoH_x^t \leq 1 \quad (30)$$

$$SoC_x^t = \frac{E_{B,x}^t}{E_B^r} \quad (31)$$

$$SoH_x^t = \frac{M_{H,x}^t}{M_H^r} \quad (32)$$

where E_B^r and M_H^r represent the rated capacity of energy and mass of hydrogen in the BESS and the tank. It should be noted that in this study, to provide fair results of energy management, an equal 50 % SoC and SoH are considered at the beginning and the end of simulations as demonstrated in (33) and (34).

$$SoC_x^{8760} = SoC_x^1 = 0.5 \quad (33)$$

$$SoH_x^{8760} = SoH_x^1 = 0.5 \quad (34)$$

where SoC_x^{8760} and SoC_x^1 are the SoC in the end ($t = 8760$) and the beginning ($t = 1$) of the study while SoH_x^{8760} and SoH_x^1 represent the SoH in the same hours of the year.

3.3. Renewable energy generation model

As clarified, this paper considers the application of WECs or FPVs beside WTs in hybrid offshore parks. Regarding the WT, in this paper, the specifications of a reference turbine with the rated capacity of $P_{WT,ref}^r$ are applied in all the studied locations. Hence, the power output potential of the WTs in hour t of simulation is calculated using (35).

$$P_{WT,P}^t = \left(n_{WT} \times \frac{P_{WT}^r}{P_{WT.ref,P}^r} \right) \times P_{WT.ref,P}^t \quad (35)$$

where n_{WT} is the number of WTs, P_{WT}^r is the rated capacity of the turbines in the studied park, and $P_{WT.ref,P}^r$ is the potential of power generation of the reference WT in hour t calculated for the location of the park. In order to calculate the wind power generation of the reference turbine, a model based on the one given in [40] is applied in this study as represented in (36).

$$P_{WT.ref,P}^t = \begin{cases} 0 & WS < WS^{in} \\ \frac{1}{2} \times C_p \times A_{WT} \times \rho \times (WS^t)^3 & WS^{in} \leq WS < WS^r \\ P_{WT.ref}^r & WS^r \leq WS < WS^{out} \\ 0 & WS \geq WS^{out} \end{cases} \quad (36)$$

where C_p is the power coefficient of the turbine, ρ is the air density, A_{WT} is the area swept by the turbine blades, and WS^t is the wind speed in hour t ; furthermore, WS^{in} , WS^r , and WS^{out} represent the cut-in, rated, and cut-out speeds of the turbine.

Regarding the WECs, in this paper, the power matrix of 400 kW CorPower WEC is applied to calculate the wave energy generation potential in the park based on the height and duration of the waves. In the power matrix, as a common framework for the calculation of the power generation capability of the WECs, a representative power is identified for each range of the height and duration of waves that is determined by the manufacturers of the device. Accordingly, in this paper, regarding the data available for the height and duration of waves in each hour, the power generation capability of the device is directly taken from the representative cell of the matrix.

Finally, regarding the FPV systems, based on the model given in [11], the power generation potential is calculated using (37).

$$P_{FPV,P}^t = n_{FPV} \times PR_{FPV} \times \eta_{FPV} \times A_{FPV} \times G^t \quad (37)$$

in which n_{FPV} is the number of FPV panels, PR_{FPV} is the performance ratio, η_{FPV} is the efficiency, A_{FPV} is the area of each panel, and G^t is the solar irradiance.

4. Solution strategy

As described in Section 3, in this work, the energy management of the hybrid offshore parks is defined as a MO problem. In order to solve the defined MO problem, in this study, a set of pairs of weights is applied to the two OFs, and the optimal results are obtained for each member of this set. It should be noted that by applying each pair of weights, the overall problem model turns into a MILP one. Hence, the conventional methods for solving MILP problems, as reliable and fast strategies, can be applied to find the optimal solution and determine one point in the Pareto front. Repeating these steps and estimating Pareto front by examining different combinational weights, Fuzzy Decision Making (FDM) is then applied to find the final solution based on the priorities of the decision-maker. The following subsections describe the implementation of the weighted sum method and the proposed strategy for forming Pareto front as well as the decision making process.

4.1. Weighted sum method for multiobjective optimization

The composite OF of a MO problem while applying the weighting factors can be represented by (38) [41].

$$\text{Minimize } U = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i \times F_i(z) \quad (38)$$

where n is the number of OFs, and w_i is the weight of F_i as the representative of i th OF that is defined by (39) and (40) in this work for OF_1 and OF_2 .

$$F_1(z) = \frac{(OF_1^{SO1} - OF_1(z))}{(OF_1^{SO1} - OF_1^{SO2})} \quad (39)$$

$$F_2(z) = \frac{(OF_2(z) - OF_2^{SO2})}{(OF_2^{SO1} - OF_2^{SO2})} \quad (40)$$

where OF_1^{SO1} and OF_2^{SO1} are values of TDE and TVP (as OF_1 and OF_2) while solving a Single Objective (SO) optimization problem with respect to (17) neglecting (18). Similarly, OF_1^{SO2} and OF_2^{SO2} are values of TDE and TVP while solving a SO optimization regarding (18) neglecting (17). Finally, it should be noted that the weights in (38) are adjusted to comply with the conditions given in (41) and (42) that indicates each of them should be positive value while the sum is equal to 1.

$$\sum_{i=1}^n w_i = 1 \quad (41)$$

$$w_i > 0 \quad (42)$$

where n is the number of OFs.

4.2. Pareto front estimation and fuzzy decision making

In order to estimate the Pareto front in this paper, similar to the strategy described in [42], a set of combinational weights is applied to the two objectives of the problem. Accordingly, for the MILP problem formed by applying each pair of weighting values, the optimization is carried out to calculate TDE and TVP. In this way, the obtained solution will have a representative in the 2D coordinate plane of the OFs. Among the solutions obtained by repeating these steps for whole specified pairs of weights, the set of non-dominated ones is selected as the Pareto front by applying the rules given in [43].

In the next step, in this paper, FDM is applied to determine the desired solution based on the descriptions given in [44]. In this method, the solution is selected among the ones in the Pareto front by solving the optimization problem defined in (43).

$$\min_{z \in \Phi} \sum_{i=1}^n |\mu_{ri} - \mu_{fi}(z)|^p \quad (43)$$

in which μ_{ri} is the reference value for the i th OF, and $\mu_{fi}(z)$ is the membership function value of the same OF calculated for a set of decision variables represented by z , and $1 \leq p < \infty$ [45].

4.3. Flowchart of the developed energy management optimization framework

Based on the descriptions, the flowchart of the overall optimization framework is represented in Fig. 5 including the Pareto front formation block that is given separately in more detail. As shown in Fig. 5.a, the solution strategy starts with loading the time-series of data for renewable energy sources (wind speed, wave height/duration, solar irradiance, etc.) and the other input data including RES size, storage scenario, parameters of the system, and the sets of the values for the weights to be

Fig. 5. Flowchart of the proposed strategy for energy management: a) overall optimization framework b) Pareto front formation.

applied in MO problem. Following this step, the first assessment is applied to the park with no-storage to identify TVP_{NS} and TDE_{NS} . In the next step, independent SO optimizations are carried out to calculate OF_1^{SO1} , OF_2^{SO1} , OF_1^{SO2} , and OF_2^{SO2} . Then, the formation of the Pareto front is addressed according to the detailed steps of Fig. 5.b; according to the flowchart, the formation of Pareto front starts with the implementation of the optimization regarding the first combination of weights. The studies are then repeated for the other combinational weights and the Pareto front is updated gradually. By finalizing the formation of Pareto front, regarding Fig. 5.a, the decision making is applied concerning the descriptions given for FDM. Supplementary calculations are then implemented on the selected solution. Finally, the outputs are printed, and the results are represented.

5. Simulation studies and the results

The proposed strategy for energy management of the hybrid offshore parks assisted with hybrid storage systems is examined in two locations regarding different storage scenarios in this section. Accordingly, in the first part of this section, the case studies are introduced. Then, the parameters applied to the studies are given and the scenarios are characterized. Finally, the results of applying the proposed energy management strategy in the parks are given and discussed. It should be noted that the optimization tool for the implementation of the proposed strategy is developed using Python programming language while applying OR-Tools [46] and Gurobi [47] to solve the MILP optimization problem. In order to calculate the renewable energy generation potential, ERA5 dataset is applied in the studies of this paper [48]. The rest of

the data and parameters applied to the optimization studies are given in Section 5.2.

5.1. Studied parks

In order to assess the two cases of combinational RESs in the hybrid parks, i.e. WT-WEC and WT-FPV, two offshore parks in the Atlantic Ocean and the North Sea are studied in this paper. The descriptions for each of the parks are given in the following subsections.

5.1.1. WindFloat Atlantic

WindFloat Atlantic is an existing offshore wind park in Portugal with a current installed capacity of 25.2 MW comprising three WT each for 8.4 MW. However, with an offshore electrical connection of 80 MW that will be even capable of operating at 150 MW capacity in the future, there is much more power capacity to be installed in the location. On the other hand, the potential of this park for wave energy generation has been already evaluated and approved in the literature [49]. Accordingly, in this paper, considering the existing 80 MW capacity of the offshore connection cable, 75 WEC units and 20 WTs (i.e. with overall capacity of 30 MW and 168 MW, respectively) are applied in this park.

5.1.2. Alpha Ventus

Alpha Ventus is an offshore wind park with an overall installed capacity of 60 MW located in the North Sea. Based on the information provided in [50], a 62 MW offshore connection capacity is also considered for this park in this study. Furthermore, regarding the ongoing projects of the offshore solar park in the North Sea that confirms

the potential of the area for this RES technology, a 300 MW FPV is considered beside the WTs in the park for the assessment of the hybrid power plants in this paper.

5.2. Simulation parameters and the studied scenarios

The other parameters applied in the simulation studies of this paper are given in this subsection. Regarding the efficiency of the BESS and FC systems, $\eta_B = 0.95$ [20] and $\eta_{FC} = 0.6$ [19] are applied in this study. The minimum allowed level of the energy stored in the BESS and the mass of hydrogen in the tank are limited by applying $SoC^{min} = 0.2$ and $SoH^{min} = 0.1$. As the other data for the H2-FC system, an approximate $ELH = 58.01$ kWh/kg [37] and $\alpha = 33$ kWh/kg [51] are applied in the studies of this paper. Regarding the rated power and the size of the storage system, $P_B^r = 10$ MW, $P_{FC}^r = 10$ MW, and $P_H^r = 30$ MW are applied while $E_B^r = 5 \times P_B^r$ and $M_H^r = 200 \times 10^3$ kg capacities are considered.

Regarding wind power generation, the specification of 8.0 MW Vestas V164 turbines are considered in this study and $\rho = 1.225$ kg/m³ [52,53] is applied as the air density. As the other parameter in the RES generation calculation, the specifications of the same panels used in [11], including the 1.6 m² area and the efficiency of 18.8 % are applied in this study while, however, a constant PR = 0.85 is considered in this work. Finally, as clarified in Section 3, it should be noted that the power matrix of CorPower 400 kW WEC is applied to calculate the wave energy generation potential in the offshore park in this work.

Regarding the constraint on TDE, represented by (24), $d_{TDE}^{min} = 1$ is applied in this paper to ensure that the delivered energy is more than the NS case regardless of the FDM reference values. Similarly, regarding the constraint on TVP represented by (25), d_{TVP}^{max} is set to 1 to ensure that the fluctuations of power are less than NS case. It should be noted that for the formation of the Pareto front, a set of weights from 0.05 to 0.95 with a step of 0.05 are applied in this paper. Furthermore, to apply the FDM, three specific cases are considered in this work as represented in Table 2.

The storage system scenarios in this paper are characterized in Table 3 and Table 4 for the different cases of electrical system capacity limitations. According to Table 3, while in STS-1 and STS-3 storage scenarios, the BESS and H2-FC systems are concentrated, the separated offshore BESS and onshore H2-FC are applied in STS-2 scenario. Regarding the electrical system capacity limitation scenarios, as shown in Table 4, in NLS-1 where the network capacity in the onshore connection point is lower than the offshore cable capacity, all storage scenarios listed in Table 3 are examined and the results are compared. This is then followed by NLS-2 case, where an identical limitation is considered in the offshore cable and the onshore connection point in which the STS-1 storage scenario is studied.

5.3. Simulation results

The simulation studies regarding the different scenarios of storage system configuration and the electrical system limitation based on Table 3 and Table 4 are implemented in this section for the two different parks described in Section 5.1 and the results are given and discussed.

5.3.1. WindFloat Atlantic

As the first study, the simulation results for WindFloat Atlantic park are given in this section. Accordingly, in the first step, the energy generation potential by the RESs in this site regarding the data of 2023 is represented in Fig. 6. This primary assessment approves the potential of

Table 2
FDM cases applied to the studies.

MO case	μ_{r1}	μ_{r2}
MO-1	Medium	Medium
MO-2	High	Low
MO-3	Low	High

Table 3

Combinational units of the hybrid storage system in the studied multi-source offshore parks.

Storage scenario	Offshore		Onshore	
	BESS	H2-FC	BESS	H2-FC
STS-1	✓	✓	×	×
STS-2	✓	×	×	✓
STS-3	×	×	✓	✓

Table 4

Storage system scenarios applied regarding the electrical system capacity limitation.

Network limitation scenario	P_N^{max}/P_C^r	Studied STS scenario		
		STS-1	STS-2	STS-3
NLS-1	0.75	✓	✓	✓
NLS-2	1	✓	×	×

wave energy sources in providing stable power for the park in this location. The energy management results regarding the different scenarios in this park are given in the following subsections.

5.3.1.1. NLS-1: network capacity less than the offshore cable. In the case of NLS-1 and the storage scenario of STS-1 in which BESS and H2-FC systems are placed in the offshore sector, the DTVP index calculated by (21) is plotted with respect to the TDE for each solution in the Pareto front in Fig. 7. The power delivered to the network in this scenario for MO-1 case is shown in Fig. 8 while being compared to the park with no storage (NS case). According to the simulation results, the overall yearly delivered energy of the park increased from 354.8 GWh in NS case to 376.7 GWh while a decrease of 80.9 % in the variation of power is also observed by applying the energy management strategy. For this case, the SoC of BESS and SoH of hydrogen tank are also plotted for the whole year in Fig. 9.

The simulation results are summarized and given for the different cases in WindFloat Atlantic park in Table 5. As it is clear in the results, in each of STS scenarios, the desired trade-off between the RES energy delivery to the network and the decrease of power variations can be provided by applying FDM on the Pareto front to find the solution of the MO optimization. Accordingly, while the highest energy is delivered in MO-2 and the least power variations are observed in MO-3, an acceptable level of improvement in both objectives is provided in MO-1.

5.3.1.2. NLS-2: Network capacity equal to the offshore cable capacity. For NLS-2 scenario, where the network limitation is equal to the capacity of the offshore cable, the DTVP and TDE for the solutions in Pareto front are shown in Fig. 10. Furthermore, the summary of results for the MO cases in NLS-2 scenario is provided in Table 6 where, as previously clarified in Table 3, the STS-1 storage scenario is studied. Similar to the previous NLS case, an acceptable trade-off is achieved between the total delivered energy and power variations regarding the applied FDM cases in this scenario as well.

5.3.1.3. Comparison of NLS-1 and NLS-2 in WindFloat Atlantic park. Comparing the results of Table 6 with the ones given in Table 5 for the NLS-1, a considerable increase of delivered energy is observed in NLS-2 that could have been anticipated due to the lower level of limitation and less curtailments. However, comparing similar FDM cases in Table 5 and Table 6, it is clear that a less decrease of the power variations is also observed in NLS-2 scenario. The first reason for such an observation is the similar FDM parameters that are applied in the two NLS scenarios while the Pareto fronts are different regarding the power variations and the delivered energy. Furthermore, the higher capacity of the network in the onshore connection point in NLS-2 case increases the potential of

Fig. 6. RES generation potential in WindFloat Atlantic park: a) wind energy b) wave energy.

Fig. 7. DTVP vs. TDE in STS-1 storage scenario of NLS-1 in WindFloat Atlantic park.

power variations considering the tendency to increase TDE as the other OF. As a result, with more energy that can be delivered directly to the network considering the less strict capacity limitation in NLS-2, there is also less contribution of the storage system in overall energy delivery, decreasing the possibility of less power variations. It should be re-emphasized that these effects can vary significantly while applying other FDM values. However, the FDM parameters are maintained identical in all the cases of this work for the sake of simplicity and the comparison of the results.

5.3.2. Alpha Ventus

The simulation results for the Alpha Ventus park are given in this section. As the first assessment on this park, the power generation potential of the RESs is shown in Fig. 11 where the seasonal complementarity of the two RESs in this location is clearly figured; this is a strong initiative of such a combinational RES implementation in this park.

The hourly power delivered to the network in the NS case is compared with the results regarding MO-optimized energy management strategy in this park in Fig. 12 for MO-1 in STS-1 storage scenario of NLS-1. For the case of this park, comparing WindFloat Atlantic, the more variations in power are clear as the effect of the higher fluctuation of FPV power compared to WECs. However, according to the results, the yearly energy delivered to the network increased from 296.7 GWh to 330.1 GWh in this park while the fluctuations decreased by 66.6 %. The

Fig. 8. Power delivered to the network in WindFloat Atlantic park in NLS-1 scenario: a) no-storage case b) with storage system in MO-1 case of STS-1.

Fig. 9. State of stored energy and hydrogen in MO-1 for STS-1 storage scenario in NLS-1 in WindFloat Atlantic park: a) SoC of BESS b) SoH of the tank.

Table 5
Park assessment results in NLS-1 scenario in WindFloat Atlantic.

	Index	FDM case		
		MO-1	MO-2	MO-3
STS-1	TDE	376.7	389.6	356.0
	DTVP	80.9 %	64.6 %	87.4 %
STS-2	TDE	372.1	381.3	355.9
	DTVP	79.5 %	61.8 %	86.8 %
STS-3	TDE	370.5	379.7	354.9
	DTVP	79.5 %	61.4 %	86.8 %

it is worth mentioning that according to the results, no time during the year is observed with no power generation applying the energy management strategy while there was a considerable time with no power in the NS case.

The Pareto fronts regarding DTVP and TDE for STS-1 scenario of NLS-1 and NLS-2 are shown in Fig. 14. A summary of the simulation results for this park in all the studied scenarios is also given in Table 7 and Table 8. According to the results, similar to the WindFloat Atlantic case, the stricter capacity limitation in NLS-1 decreases the deviations of power like a filter on the output of the park. However, this has led to a considerable decrease in the delivered energy. Furthermore, as it is clear in the results, applying the decision-making strategy, an acceptable trade-off between the delivered energy of the park and the power variations can be provided by the MO optimization in the presence of the hybrid BESS and H2-FC system in all the storage and network limitation scenarios.

6. Conclusion

In this paper, a multiobjective framework is proposed for the energy management of the hybrid offshore wind-wave and wind-photovoltaic parks assisted with battery, hydrogen, and fuel cell storage systems considering the capacity limitation of the offshore cable and the onshore connection point with the inland electrical grid. The proposed methodology aims at maximizing the energy delivered to the network while minimizing the overall variations of power. An optimization tool is developed to assess the effectiveness of the proposed strategy for energy management. The simulation studies are implemented in the location of two offshore parks in the Atlantic Ocean and the North Sea and the results are discussed. According to the results, in the different studied scenarios of the location of the storage units and the capacity limitation of the system, the developed multiobjective strategy can provide a trade-off between the RES energy delivered to the network and the power variations. This is examined with regard to different combinations of RESs and through a series of fuzzy decision making experiments to address various scenarios of the hybrid sources in the park as well as the priorities in implementing the energy management strategy. The results for all the cases approved the effectiveness of the method in energy management of multi-source offshore parks in the presence of hybrid storage systems. According to the results, in the WindFloat Atlantic park, the yearly energy can be increased from 354.8 MWh up to 389.6 MWh with 64.6 % less power variation in the stricter network limitation case studied in the paper. Furthermore, if more stable output power is expected, an over 80 % decrease in the variations can also be provided in the other solutions of multi-objective energy management. Although the results are affected by the scenarios of network limitation and the location of the storage units, all of them show the trade-off can be successfully provided by applying the developed method for multiobjective energy management of the multi-source offshore parks. However, focusing on the energy generation and the fluctuations of the power in this study, further assessments are needed to evaluate the economic feasibility of the energy storage strategy considering the cost of batteries

Fig. 10. DTVP vs. TDE in STS-1 storage scenario of NLS-2 in WindFloat Atlantic park.

Table 6
Park assessment results in NLS-2 scenario in WindFloat Atlantic park.

	Index	FDM case		
		MO-1	MO-2	MO-3
STS-1	TDE	440.2	449.6	420.1
	TVPR	72.6 %	55.2 %	82.1 %

energy stored in the BESS and the hydrogen mass in the tank for this case are also shown in Fig. 13. According to these results, the excess energy in the first half of the year is not enough to maintain an acceptable level of stored hydrogen for most of the time in this period. This could have been observed in Fig. 11 where the solar power generation is very low at the beginning of the year. This is then followed by a period of time where the wind power generation is low and the excess FPV power is stored in the BESS and the H2 tank mostly to supply power in hours with no solar generation in the same day or a few ones later. However, as time progresses, the higher levels of energy are also stored in the tank for the supply of power over longer time scales as is clear in the results. Finally,

Fig. 11. RES generation potential in Alpha Ventus park: a) wind energy b) solar photovoltaic energy.

Fig. 12. Power delivered to the network in Alpha Ventus park in NLS-1 scenario: a) no-storage case b) with storage system in MO-1 case of STS-1.

Fig. 13. State of stored energy and hydrogen in MO-1 for STS-1 storage scenario in NLS-1 in Alpha Ventus park: a) SoC of BESS b) SoH of the tank.

Fig. 14. DTVP vs. TDE in STS-1 storage scenario in Alpha Ventus park in a) NLS-1 b) NLS-2.

Table 7
Simulation results in NLS-1 scenario in Alpha Ventus park.

	Index	FDM case		
		MO-1	MO-2	MO-3
STS-1	TDE	330.1	339.6	303.3
	DTVP	66.6 %	57.0%	82.0%
STS-2	TDE	321.4	329.9	301.1
	DTVP	68.8 %	55.5 %	82.7 %
STS-3	TDE	313.6	325.6	296.7
	DTVP	72.9 %	53.0%	83.8 %

Table 8
Simulation results in NLS-2 scenario in Alpha Ventus park.

	Index	FDM case		
		MO-1	MO-2	MO-3
STS-1	TDE	387.1	397.6	369.5
	TVPR	58.5 %	44.6 %	69.3 %

and the hydrogen/fuel-cell systems and the energy market price scenarios in future works. The effect of forecasting strategies, whether for the determination of renewable energy generation potential or the market prices, on the effective implementation of the developed energy management strategy should also be assessed and will be implemented in future works. This will be finally followed by the assessments on the optimal size of the storage systems with respect to the size of the existing park and the capacity of the electrical infrastructure as a future work of the authors.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Ehsan Kazemi-Robati: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Sofia Varotto:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Bernardo Silva:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis. **Irina Temiz:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial

interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

The authors do not have permission to share data.

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